

MOBIDATALAB

Labs for prototyping future mobility data sharing solutions in the cloud

| D1.7 Report on Expert Committee Activities

01/02/2024

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Summary sheet

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Abstract	This document is the D1.7 deliverable named “Report on Expert Committee Activities” which aims to provide a single and whole document referring all activities from Year 1 (2021) to Year 3 (2024) of the MobiDataLab project. This deliverable addresses the activities and support made by the Expert Committee all long the project.

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Project partners

Organisation	Country	Abbreviation
AKKODIS	France	AKKODIS
CONSORZIO INTERUNIVERSITARIO PER L'OTTIMIZZAZIONE E LA RICERCA OPERATIVA	Italy	ICOOR
AETHON SYMVOULI MICHANIKI MONOPROSOPI IKE	Greece	AETHON
CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	Italy	CNR
HOVE	France	HOVE
HERE GLOBAL B.V.	Netherlands	HERE
KATHOLIEKE UNIVERSITEIT LEUVEN	Belgium	KUL
UNIVERSITAT ROVIRA I VIRGILI	Spain	URV
POLIS - PROMOTION OF OPERATIONAL LINKS WITH INTEGRATED SERVICES	Belgium	POLIS
F6S NETWORK IRELAND LIMITED	Ireland	F6S

Document history

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0.2	08-01 to 22-01-24	AKKODIS	All	Contribution
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Executive Summary

MobiDataLab WP1 (Project Management) aims to develop an effective and comprehensive technical, administrative and financial management that ensures the successful execution of the MobiDataLab project and the achievements of its objectives.

This document is the D1.7 deliverable named “Report on Expert Committee Activities” which aims to provide a single and whole document referring all activities from Year 1 (2021) to Year 3 (2024) of the MobiDataLab project. This document describes in detail the different activities and themes on which the experts have worked on and participated in. It addresses the activities and support made by the Expert Committee all along the project.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
AB	Advisory Board
CINEA	The European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
D	Deliverable
EC	Executive Committee
GA	General Assembly
KB	Knowledge Base
LL	Living Labs
M	Month
OKB	Open Knowledge Base
PO	Project Officer
RG	Reference Group
T	Task
TL	Task Leader
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

1.1. Project overview

There has been an explosion of mobility services and data sharing in recent years. Building on this, the EU-funded MobiDataLab project works to foster the sharing of data among transport authorities, operators and other mobility stakeholders in Europe. MobiDataLab develops knowledge as well as a cloud solution aimed at easing the sharing of data. Specifically, the project is based on a continuous co-development of knowledge and technical solutions. It collects and analyses the advice and recommendations of experts and supporting cities, regions, clusters and associations. These actions are assisted by the incremental construction of a cross-thematic knowledge base and a cloud-based service platform, which will improve access and usage of data sharing resources.

1.2. Purpose of the deliverable

The objective of this deliverable is to make a report on the activities of the committee of experts who have been working as external experts for the MobiDataLab project on specific themes related to the WP2, WP3 and WP5 mainly. This document reports the interactions with the members of the consortium, including results of the working meetings.

This expert committee worked on different themes related to the deliverables from:

- WP2 (with a security & data privacy group, standards, cloud services & technologies, use cases, legal & governance).
- WP3, a group of business models & societal impacts.
- WP5, the working group will be for the Virtual Lab and open tools group.

This deliverable is related to the Task T1.5 – Expert Committee Management.

1.3. Structure of the deliverable and its relationship with other work packages/deliverables

This deliverable addresses:

- Global information
- The Expert Committee
- Phase 1 - Knowledge Base Review (2021-2022)
- Phase 2 - Living Labs Review (2023)

It will end with the conclusion.

1.4. Intended audience

The dissemination level of this deliverable is Public ('PU') and its intended audience is therefore any person interested in knowing about the advisory process set up by the project.

1.5. MobiDataLab project partners

The MobiDataLab project involves 10 partners from several countries and from different types of organisation (association, SMEs, industries, universities, research centres with multidisciplinary expertise) with different types of responsibilities, as shown in the table below:

Table 1 - MobiDataLab Project partners & Roles

Partner	Country	Type	Main role in MobiDataLab
AKKODIS (Previously AKKA)	FR	Solution provider	Lead on the orchestration of the requirements for the transport cloud prototype. Specific know-how in distributed data sharing architectures and geospatial data.
ICOOR-UNIMORE	IT	Research Institute	Lead on the business analysis and impact assessment of the data sharing culture. Strong expertise in ICT and transport related research projects.
AETHON	GR	Solution provider	Contribution to the development of new smart mobility solutions and the development of the Virtual Lab. Lead on the Living Lab Instance 3 (Codagon).
CNR	IT	Research Institute	Lead research activities in data processing notably federated cloud solutions and semantic enrichment methods for the Transport Cloud Prototype.
HOVE (Previously KISIO)	FR	Solution provider	Provision of a dedicated open API (Navitia.io) for data sharing in transport. Lead on the Exploitation activities. Lead on the Living Lab Instance 2 (Hackathon).
HERE	NL	Solution provider	Data and platform provider specialized in spatial data. Lead on the Living Lab Instance 1 (Datathon).
KUL	BE	University	Lead on the legal and regulatory landscape analysis for data sharing practices.

URV	ES	University	Lead on the data privacy aspects (overall analysis, requirements and development).
POLIS	BE	Association / Network	Stakeholder engagement with a strong focus on Smart Cities as potential users of the MobiDataLab solutions. Lead on the Dissemination and Communication activities.
F6S	IR	Association / Network	Lead on the engagement activities and notably building ecosystems of start-ups and SMEs as users of the MobiDataLab solutions.

1.6. Structure of MobiDataLab

As a reminder, it may be important to recall the general project management structure chosen for the MobiDataLab implementation, and how the Expert Committee fits in this structure. Two different decision levels have actually been defined:

- the strategic level, with the General Assembly formed by the Coordinator and a representative of each partner, dealing with the strategic orientations of the project, giving scientific orientations, developing plans and allocating the funds,
- the executive level with the Coordinator and the Work Package Leaders (WPLs) implementing the developments of the work plan.

The Advisory Board (as well as the Reference Group of Municipalities, which is not covered in this document but in the D6.5 report) are mainly involved at a strategic level, providing advice on technical, economic, societal and other issues.

Figure 1 - Global Management Structure of the MobiDataLab project

1.7. About the Workpackage, Task, Deliverable, Milestone, Leader, Participants, Risk, Duration

This deliverable is part of the **Workpackage** 1 which addresses all the administrative and financial aspects of the project including the experts' activities.

Figure 2 - PERT (Program Evaluation & Review Technique) chart of the MobiDataLab project

The corresponding **Task** is the T1.5 – Expert Committee Management, and the related **Deliverable** is D1.7 – Report on Expert Committee Activities. The corresponding **Duration** represents to the total length of the project from M1 (February 2021) to M36 (January 2024).

The Task Leader is AKKODIS and the only Task Participant identified in the Grant Agreement is AETHON. POLIS also contributed to this task since there is a link with Task 6.4 “Multi-stakeholder group creation and coordination” and the public transport authorities collaborating with the project in this context. In operational terms, AKKODIS worked on this task throughout the 3 years of the project. AETHON, as leader of WP5, and POLIS were involved in year 3 mainly – the last year of the project corresponding to the organisational activities of the living labs. The specific importance of WP5 with respect to the Expert Committee was to establish a link between the Advisory Board members and the evaluation of the Living Labs results (Hackathon, Datathon & Codagon).

The specific collaboration of AKKODIS and AETHON, also with the help of POLIS, on Task 1.5 aimed to address questions like how to make the Advisory Board members participate in the Living Labs, what kind of help they can best provide to the consortium, which of the Advisory Board Members would preferably be involved in the Living Labs' evaluation, etc.

2. The Expert Committee – Advisory Board members and Consortium experts

The MobiDataLab Expert Committee is basically constituted of :

- Experts of the consortium both from the operations and the research domains,
- Experts from other projects and initiatives dealing with mobility data and data sharing, acting on reports, frameworks, actions, and communities with high added value in the field of transport.

2.1. Advisory Board of external experts

An Advisory Board has been created and composed of several individual experts from the transport and data sharing ecosystems, and notably from past/ongoing R&D projects. The main role of the Advisory Board was to provide the MobiDataLab Consortium with specific advices and strategic orientations in order to guide the developments of the project, especially for the development of the Open Knowledge Base and the evaluation of the Living Labs.

The members of the Advisory Board were invited by the project to join dedicated workshops online, for the Knowledge Base evaluation, and to participate on site in the living labs, for their evaluation. Experts have been appointed as Knowledge Base reviewers, as Living Labs reviewers, or as both.

2.1.1. Knowledge Base Reviewers

In the first phase of the collaboration with external experts, the main activity of the advisory Board was to review the MobiDataLab deliverables related to WP2 (“Open Knowledge Base”) and part of WP3 (“New data sharing services and business models”).

Six working groups have been defined and proposed to the experts, related to WP2 and WP3 : Data privacy and Security, Legal and governance, Standards, Socio-economic and environmental analysis, Use cases (more details in the next section).

The following experts were invited, because of their knowledge of the sector and their expertise in one or more of the above domains:

- Guido di PASQUALE – UITP¹
- Gabriel PLASSAT – la Fabrique des Mobilités²
- Pedro BARRADAS – ARMIS³ ITS

¹ UITP | Union Internationale du Transport Public | <https://www.uitp.org/>

² <https://lafabriquedesmobilites.fr/>

³ <https://www.armisgroup.com/>

- Stephane DREHER – ERTICO⁴ and Oxsys consulting
- Piia KARJALAINEN – MaaS alliance secretary general – ERTICO
- Leo FRACHET – MobilityData⁵
- Tu-Tho THAI – Manager, Projects & Partnerships – MobilityData
- Julien de LABACA – le Facilitateur de Mobilité ⁶
- Jordi SORIA COMAS – APDCAT⁷

Each working group of the Expert Committee contributed to the Knowledge Base, consolidating all the information (reports, best practices, standards, open source code, open datasets) from the most important projects and initiatives implemented to date in the domain of transport data sharing. They also helped to contextualize relevant use cases, corresponding to concrete issues of the stakeholders of the Reference Group.

2.1.2. Living Labs Reviewers

In the second phase of the collaboration with external experts, the main activity of the Advisory Board was to review the MobiDataLab's living lab instances. Hence the alternative naming of "review committee" responsible for evaluating the innovative solutions to mobility challenges submitted by the participants.

The events, in a hybrid format, allowed virtual participation but physical attendance was encouraged. We allocated a budget for the travel of experts to the x-athons (Virtual and Living Labs). Because of the specific nature of this exercise and the fact that it is more difficult to obtain time (it is preferable to be present on site), we have extended the invitations.

The following experts were invited:

- Tu-Tho THAI – Manager, Projects & Partnerships – ITxPT⁸
- Lucie KIRSTEIN – Team Lead at National Academy of Science & Engineering – Acatech⁹
- Ferdinand BURGERSDIJK – Coach & Mentor for digital transformation in mobility – FRCB¹⁰
- Stijin VERMAILLEN – City of Antwerp
- Thomas GEIER – Policy Advisor – EMTA¹¹
- Vincent LAU – City of Amsterdam
- Bertrand BILLOUD – Responsible of Open data platforms and content – SNCF¹²

⁴ ERTICO | European Road Transport Telematics Implementation Coordination | <https://ertico.com/>

⁵ <https://mobilitydata.org/>

⁶ <https://www.juliendelabaca.com/>

⁷ APDCAT | Autoritat Catalana de Proteccio de Dades | <https://apdcatal.gencat.cat/>

⁸ <https://itxpt.org/>

⁹ <https://www.acatech.de/>

¹⁰ <https://www.frcb.nl/>

¹¹ EMTA | European Metropolitan Transport Authorities | <https://www.emta.com/>

¹² SNCF | Société Nationale des Chemins de fer Français | <https://www.sncf.com/>

- Ross DOUGLAS – CEO Autonomy Paris & the Urban Mobility Weekly – Autonomy Paris¹³
- Annie KORTSARI – Head of Rail Transport Systems & Services laboratory – CERTH¹⁴
- David JONIETZ – Axon Vibe¹⁵
- Salim BENKIRANE – Policy Officer – ALL RAIL¹⁶

2.2. Consortium experts

In addition to the external experts, researchers from the consortium were appointed to carry out the various reviews and assessments of the work of their peers and/or third parties involved in the project, for example as part of the WP5 innovation sessions or Living Labs.

2.2.1. Knowledge Base reviewers

The following consortium partners participated in the review of the WP2/WP3 deliverables (column Peer Reviewers). Each partner has appointed a representative to carry out the review, depending on their expertise and availability at the time of the review.

Table 2 - Peer Reviewers of MobiDataLab Deliverables

Deliverable	Due Month	Peer Reviewers		Expertise description
D2.1	M12	ICOOR	POLIS	Legal and Regulatory Requirements to be validated by transport regulation experts (POLIS) and EU project experts (ICOOR)
D2.3	M6	AKKODIS	CNR	Data Privacy Requirements to be validated by the Transport Cloud WP4 leader (AKKODIS) and architecture leader (CNR)
D2.4	M6	AETHON	KUL	Standard Requirements to be validated by AETHON in conformity with the EU regulations (KUL)
D2.6	M6	ICOOR	F6S	Frameworks can be related to tech startups/events (F6S) or EU projects (ICOOR)
D2.7	M15 instead of M12	AKKODIS	CNR	Data governance mechanisms can be related to technical solutions (AKKODIS, CNR)
D2.9	M6	HOVE	POLIS	Reviewing use cases is interesting for reference group management (POLIS) and public transport expert (HOVE)
D3.1	M6	HOVE	POLIS	Actors' needs to be validated by a partner knowledgeable about the public authorities needs (POLIS) and about the Public Transport Operators needs (HOVE)

¹³ <https://www.autonomy.paris/>

¹⁴ CERTH | Center for Research and Technologies Hellas | <https://www.certh.gr/>

¹⁵ <https://axonvibe.com/>

¹⁶ <https://www.allrail.eu/>

D3.2	M6	CNR	F6S	Data sharing market report to be validated by a partner knowledgeable about market studies (F6S) and by the leader of Task 2.4 working on the same frameworks (CNR)
D3.3	M10	AETHON	AKKODIS	Market Gap analysis to be validated by the exploitation plan task leader (AKKODIS) and Actors needs task leader (AETHON)
D3.4	M15	AETHON	POLIS	Data Sharing business and revenue models to be validated by Actors needs task leader (AETHON) and reference group of stakeholders (POLIS)
D3.5	M15	HERE	KUL	Societal and Environmental Impacts to be validated by geodata experts (HERE) and public policy expert (KUL)

2.2.2. Living Labs reviewers

The following consortium experts participated in the review of one or several of the Living Lab instances:

- Anna KONTINI (AETHON)
- Thierry CHEVALLIER (AKKODIS)
- Johannes LAUER (HERE)
- Laura BABIO SOMOZA (POLIS)
- Benjamin PLOT (HOVE)

2.3. The Expert Committee

2.3.1. Role of the Expert Committee

The role of the Expert Committee was to give technical, societal & business counsel to the members of the consortium.

The experts reviewed and worked on dedicated deliverables in order to improve their content before submission to the European Commission portal (CINEA), and they reviewed the outcomes of the virtual and living labs.

3. Phase 1 – Knowledge Base Review (2021-2022)

3.1. Working Groups

Six **working groups** have been defined and proposed to the experts. The themes are related to WP2 and WP3:

- **Data privacy and Security:** responsible for identifying main privacy and security issues associated to data sharing, including preventing data misuse.
- **Legal and governance:** responsible for comparing the transportation data regulation across all transport modes in the EU and identifying appropriate governance for the establishment of a possible Transport Cloud.
- **Standards:** responsible for identifying the standards and specifications that have been adopted by the EU or nationally.
- **Cloud services & technologies:** in charge of evaluating the different solutions for transport in terms of competitiveness, accessibility, etc.
- **Socio-economic and environmental analysis:** contributing to the definition of the most relevant use cases and the related transport flows in which digitalization and data sharing could provide more economic and environmental impact, to the identification of best practices in stakeholders' collaborations.
- Use cases

3.2. Expertise and work on deliverables

3.2.1. Expertise, Fees, and Organisations involved

In phase 1, the experts worked on deliverables of M6 (July 2021) and M15 (April 2022), see tables below. A fee of €450 excluding VAT per day was offered to experts who wished to be remunerated. Some experts preferred to work on a voluntary basis, following the recommendations of their organisation.

Different kinds of organisations are involved on the review of deliverables such as associations/non-profit organisations, public entities, large companies, private consulting companies, small and medium-sized enterprises, etc.

Table 3 - Phase 1 – M6 Review of WP2 Deliverables & Experts organisations

Month	Deliverable	Members of the advisory Board
M6 June 2021	D2.3 – State of the art on mobility & transport data technologies / Task T2.2	Jordi SORIA COMAS Association/Public Entity: APDCAT (Spain)
	D2.4 – State of the art on data sharing standards / Task T2.3	Tu-Tho THAI Non-Profit Organization: MOBILITY DATA (France) Pedro BARRADAS Large Enterprise: ARMIS (Portugal)
	D2.6 – Report on enabling technologies for the Transport Cloud / Task T2.4	Stéphane DREHER Private consulting Company: OXSYS SPRL
	D2.9 – Use cases def V1 / Task T2.6	Julien de LABACA Private consulting Company : LE FACILITATEUR DE MOBILITE (France) Pedro BARRADAS Large Enterprise : ARMIS (Portugal)

Table 4 - Phase 1 – M15 Review of WP2 + WP3 Deliverables & Experts organisations

Month	Deliverable	Members of the advisory Board
M15 April 2022	D2.7 – Data Governance Assessment / Task T2.5	Stéphane DREHER Private Consulting Company: OXSYS SPRL
	D3.4 – Data sharing business & revenue models / Task 3.4	Gabriel PLASSAT Association/ Private Consulting Company : LA FABRIQUE DES MOBILITES (France) Guido di PASQUALE Association/Public Entity: UITP (Belgium)

3.2.2. M6 Deliverables – July 2021

The deliverables on which experts worked on for M6 (July 2021) are:

- D2.3 – State of the Art on Mobility & Transport data protection technologies
- D2.4 – State of the Art on Mobility Data Sharing Standards
- D2.6 – Report on enabling technologies for Transport Cloud
- D2.9 – Use Cases Definition V1

All these deliverables were reviewed by the experts and submitted in July 2021 on the European Commission portal.

Table 5 - Deliverables on which Experts worked on for M6 (July 2021)

WORKING GROUPS						
Working Group	Deliverable(s)	Review Slot (For Information)	Date of Submission	Project Month	Status	Deliverable Ref
Data privacy and Security	State of the art on Mobility and Transport data protection technologies provide an updated state-of-the-art review of the protection technologies. It will provide some guidance on the future developments in the project.	15-30 Jun 2021	31/07/2021	M6	Done	D2.3
Standards	State of the art on Mobility Data sharing standards provide an updated state-of-the-art review on existing standards. This will provide guidance for the developments in the project and identify gaps to solve.	15-30 Jun 2021	31/07/2021	M6	Done	D2.4
Cloud services and technologies	Report on enabling technologies for Transport Cloud provide and outlook on promising enabling technologies for Mobility and Transport data sharing.	15-30 Jun 2021	31/07/2021	M6	Done	D2.6
Use cases	Use cases definition (v1) define the use cases and associated requirements that will later addressed in the Living Lab instances.	15-30 Jun 2021	31/07/2021	M6	Done	D2.9

3.2.2.1. D2.3 – State of the Art on Mobility & Transport data protection technologies

The deliverable D2.3 was related to the “Data Privacy & Security” Working group. It aimed to provide an updated state-of-the-art review of the protection technologies. It guided the developments of the project. One expert worked on the review of this deliverable:

- Jordi SORIA COMAS (APDCAT)

3.2.2.2. D2.4 – State of the Art on Mobility data sharing Standards

The deliverable D2.4 was related to the “Standards” Working group. Its aim was to provide an updated state-of-the-art review on existing standards. This guided the development of the project and identified gaps to solve. Two experts worked on the review of this deliverable:

- Tu-Tho THAI (MobilityData)
- Pedro BARRADAS (ARMIS ITS)

3.2.2.3. D2.6 – Report on enabling technologies for the Transport Cloud

The deliverable D2.6 was related to the “Cloud Services & Technologies” Working group. The D2.6 provided and outlook on promising enabling technologies for Mobility and Transport data sharing. One expert worked on the review of this deliverable:

- Stephane DREHER (ERTICO / OXSYS)

3.2.2.4. D2.9 – Use Cases Definition V1

The deliverable D2.9 is related to the “Uses-Cases” Working group. It defined the use cases and associated requirements that were addressed in the Living Lab instances. Two experts worked on the review of this deliverable:

- Julien de LABACA (Le facilitateur de Mobilité)
- Pedro BARRADAS (ARMIS ITS)

3.2.3. M15 Deliverables – April 2022

The deliverables on which experts worked on for M15 (April 2022) were:

- D2.7 – Data Governance Assessment (WP2)
- D3.4 – Data Sharing Business & Revenue Models (WP3)

These deliverables were submitted in April 2022 on the European Commission portal.

3.2.3.1. D2.7 – Data Governance Assessment

The deliverable D2.7 was related to the “Legal & Governance” Working group. It provided an interdisciplinary outlook on the success or failure factors of the respective data governance mechanisms. It should be noted that D2.7 was initially due on M12 (January 2022) and was postponed to M15 (April 2022) with the approval of the Project Officer. One expert worked on the review of this deliverable:

- Stephane DREHER (ERTICO / OXSYS)

3.2.3.2. D3.4 – Data Sharing Business & Revenue Models

The deliverable D3.4 was related to the “Business models & Societal impact” Working group. It compiled a set of business and revenue models for the stakeholders interested in enhancing their data sharing products and services (especially: Data Providers, Service Providers, Governments) through the MobiDataLab Transport Cloud. Two experts worked on the review of this deliverable:

- Gabriel PLASSAT (la Fabrique des Mobilités)
- Guido di PASQUALE (UITP)

4. Phase 2 – Living Labs Review (2023)

4.1. Living Labs

Three living-lab instances were organised, each with a unique format:

- Datathon, 15-16 May 2023 in Berlin
- Hackathon, 14-15 September 2023 in Paris
- Codagon, starting on 6 November 2023 and finishing on 27-28 November 2023 in Leuven, together with the POLIS conference

4.2. Expertise and travel fees

During the Phase 2, the members of the review committee were asked to evaluate the solutions presented by the x-athon participants and help the consortium determine the winners of each instance. The events, in a hybrid format, allowed virtual participation but physical attendance was encouraged. A budget was allocated for covering the travel expenses and therefore the experts have been refunded.

4.2.1. Living Lab #1 – Datathon in Berlin (May 2023)

4.2.1.1. Experts' activities

The evaluators welcomed the participants to the datathon in Berlin and explained the expectations from the point of view of challenge providers and transport stakeholders in general. The presence of the evaluators and the MobiDataLab team on site contributed greatly to fruitful discussions and guidance for the participants. The experts assessed the submissions individually, then harmonised the scores before returning them to the participants and awarding the prizes.

The evaluation process took place in a separate room with 8 evaluators.

Three external experts were present, on site, at the event:

- Tu-Tho THAI (ITxPT)
- Lucie KIRSTEIN (Acatech)
- Ferdinand BURGERSDIJK (FRCB)

One external expert participated remotely:

- Stijin VERMAILLEN (City of Antwerp)

Four consortium experts were on site:

- Laura BABIO SOMOZA (POLIS)
- Anna KONTINI (AETHON)
- Johannes LAUER (HERE)
- Thierry CHEVALLIER (AKKODIS)

| DATATHON – May 2023

1st LL – LIVING LABS

3rd year
ADVISE
 Hackathons
 Datathons
 Recommendations
LIVING LABS

<https://mobidatalab.eu/living-labs/datathon/>

EXTERNAL EXPERTS

Name/Surname	Entity	Country
Tu-Tho THAI	ITxPT	FRANCE
Lucie KIRSTEIN	ACATECH	GERMANY
Ferdinand BURGERSDIJK	FRCB	NETHERLANDS

Where and When?

May 19 - 18

On-site in Berlin

Venue: Schlosspark Berlin – Schwarzkopfbühlade 11, 10115 Berlin

- Monday: 15th Afternoon (starting at 2PM CET)
- Tuesday: 16th Full day + Evening

or Online

Connection information will be provided following the registration

Figure 5 – Living Lab #1 – DATATHON – External experts ON SITE at the time of the event

4.2.1.1. Datathon report

These activities are described in detail in the related deliverable D5.6 “Report on Datathon”, under the lead of HERE (Task 5.4 leader). The initial date of submission was M26 (March 2023). It was postponed to M28 (May 2023) with the approval of the Project Officer.

It should be noted that the dissemination level of this deliverable is “Confidential” and can only be accessed by members of the consortium and the Commission Services.

4.2.2. Living Lab #2 – Hackathon in Paris (September 2023)

4.2.2.1. Experts' activities

Following the Datathon, the Living Labs organization team managed to extend the number of reviewers present on site, resulting in a diverse and multidisciplinary panel. The diversity of background and expertise allowed productive and exchanges during the jury deliberations.

Prior to the event, a webinar was organised to enable experts to understand the evaluation criteria by which they should fairly score the solutions proposed by participants.

Figure 6 – Living Lab #2 – HACKATHON – Evaluation Criteria

Following the feedback from the Datathon Review Committee, a pitching session was organised for the participants, and the jury members were offered a Q&A session immediately following each pitch.

Twelve solutions were submitted during the Hackathon. As for the datathon, the experts assessed the submissions individually, then harmonised the scores before returning them to the participants and awarding the prizes.

The review process itself was setup in a separate room with 13 reviewers.

Seven external experts were present, on site, at the event:

- Tu-Tho THAI (ITxPT)
- Lucie KIRSTEIN (Acatech)
- Ferdinand BURGERSDIJK (FRCB)
- Thomas GEIER (EMTA)
- Vincent LAU (City of Amsterdam)
- Bertrand BILLOUD (SNCF)
- Ross DOUGLAS (Autonomy Paris)

Two external experts participated remotely:

- Annie KORTSARI (CERTH)
- Stijin VERMAILLEN (City of Antwerp)

Four consortium experts were on site:

- Anna KONTINI (AETHON)
- Suzanne HOADLEY (POLIS)
- Thierry CHEVALLIER (AKKODIS)
- Benjamin PLOT (HOVE)

HACKATHON – Sept 2023

2nd – LIVING LABS

EXTERNAL EXPERTS

Name/Surname	Entity	Country
Tu-Tho THAI	ITxPT	FRANCE
Lucie KIRSTEIN	ACATECH	GERMANY
Thomas GEIER	EMTA	AUSTRIA
Vincent LAU	City of Amsterdam	NETHERLANDS
Ferdinand BURGERSDIJK	FRCB	NETHERLANDS

<https://mobidatalab.eu/living-labs/hackathon/>

Where and When?

Friday 15th and Saturday 16th of September

Hybrid: On-site in Paris & online

Venue: MakeSense – 11 Rue Biscornet, 75012 Paris.

The place is located one street from Place de la Bastille and a few minutes' walk from Gare de Lyon.

Figure 7 – Living Lab #2 – HACKATHON – External experts ON SITE at the event

4.2.2.2. Hackathon report

These activities are described in detail in the related deliverable D5.7 “Report on Hackathon”, under the lead of HOVE (Task 5.5 leader). It should be noted that the dissemination level of this deliverable is “Confidential” and can only be accessed by members of the consortium and the Commission Services.

4.2.3. Living Lab #3 – Codagon in Leuven (November 2023)

4.2.3.1. Experts’ activities

As for the Datathon and Hackathon, the Codagon solutions evaluation process also involved the Review Committee for assessing and ranking the innovative solutions submitted by participants. The Codagon evaluation criteria were once again shared with the review committee members as well as their roles and responsibilities, ensuring a standardized and consistent evaluation process.

The difference here is that the evaluation process took place entirely online, in combination with the online pitching session held on 2023 November 22nd.

A total of 11 innovative solutions were submitted by the participants and evaluated by the reviewers. Review committee members were able to score the solutions based on predefined criteria, and after the pitching session deliberated on their evaluations to reach a consensus on the final scores for all the teams.

The week following the evaluation, an award ceremony was organised in Leuven where the experts were invited to join.

7 External experts as reviewers & members of the Jury:

- Tu-Tho THAI (ITxPT)
- Ferdinand BURGERSDIJK (FRCB)
- Thomas GEIER (EMTA)
- David JONIETZ (Axon Vibe)
- Salim BENKIRANE (ALL RAIL)
- Lucie KIRSTEIN (Acatech)
- Annie KORTSARI (CERTH)

3 Consortium experts:

- Anna KONTINI (AETHON)
- Johannes LAUER (HERE)
- Thierry CHEVALLIER (AKKODIS)

CODAGON – Nov 2023

3rd LL – LIVING LABS

3rd year
 ADVISE
 Hackathons
 Datathons
 Recommendations
 LIVING LABS

<https://mobidatalab.eu/living-labs/codagon/>

EXTERNAL EXPERTS

Name/Surname	Entity	Country
Tu-Tho THAI	ITxPT	FRANCE
Ferdinand BURGERSDIJK	FRCB	NETHERLANDS
Thomas GEIER	EMTA	AUSTRIA
David JONIETZ	AXON VIBE	SWITZERLAND

Where and When?

- Online Kick off webinar on November 6, 2023
- Remote Programming period from November 6 to November 21, 2023
- Online Pitching sessions on November 22, 23 and 24, 2023
- Award ceremony in Leuven on November 27, 2023.

Venue: KU Leuven (LIM-SADL), Aula Emma Vorlat, E. Van Evenstraat 4, Leuven

MOBIDATALAB

CODAGON AGENDA

EVENT LIST FOR THE 3 WEEK ONLINE EXPERIENCE

Figure 8 – Living Lab #3 – CODAGON – External experts ON SITE at the time of the event

The following external reviewers attended the award ceremony in Leuven, Belgium, on 27 Nov 2023:

- Tu-Tho THAI (ITxPT)
- Ferdinand BURGERSDIJK (FRCB)
- Thomas GEIER (EMTA)
- David JONIETZ (Axon Vibe)

4.2.3.2. Codagon report

These activities are described in detail in the related deliverable D5.8 “Report on Codagon”, under the lead of AETHON (Task 5.6 leader). It should be noted that the dissemination level of this deliverable is “Confidential” and can only be accessed by members of the consortium and the Commission Services.

5. Conclusion

Throughout the project, the participation of all the experts was invaluable. They were a key element in the success of the project, working closely with the members of the consortium, and contributing their unfailing expertise both in reviewing our deliverables on the state of the art (phase 1 of the expertise or advisory board), but also and above all in evaluating the solutions submitted during our Living Labs (phase 2 of their support through the review committee).

In total, no fewer than seven experts worked on reviewing as many deliverables, and fifteen experts took part in evaluating more than thirty innovative solutions to mobility data challenges.

It was very important for the project to benefit from the external viewpoint of such qualified experts, which enabled us to guarantee the quality of our work on the knowledge base while at the same time ensuring that the ethics involved in evaluating the solutions were as neutral as possible. This central task of the project enabled the consortium to benefit from crucial specialist support, which contributed greatly to the success of the MobiDataLab.

MobiDataLab consortium

The consortium of MobiDataLab consists of 10 partners with multidisciplinary and complementary competencies. This includes leading universities, networks and industry sector specialists.

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#MobiDataLab

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/mobidatalab>

For further information please visit www.mobidatalab.eu

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